

Studies on Manganese Dioxide Powder Electrode Potentials

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The powder electrode potentials using manganese dioxide, prepared under different conditions, as the powder phase have been measured in presence of different concentrations of reference electrolyte solutions. Parallel studies on surface areas of the powders, adsorption property, catalytic activity in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide, have also been made with the object of drawing possible qualitative correlations between powder potentials of the different varieties on the one hand and specific surface areas, energies of activation etc on the other. Similarities exist in the sequence of increase in the powder potentials of the different samples and the sequence of increase or decrease of specific surface areas of the powders and of energies and entropies of activation.

In a previous communication¹ results of measurements of powder electrode potential with barium sulphate were presented. Tomassi and others^{2,3} contended from numerous measurements that powder electrode potentials often served as guide for characterisation of the surface nature of powders. According to Tomassi⁴ the use of powder electrodes "consists in its being a very uncomplicated method for distinguishing finely divided substances of identical or very similar composition, but differing in surface or internal structure." The study of powder electrode potentials with semiconductor powders has, in many cases, been followed up by Tomassi and others with kinetic experiments⁵, adsorption studies and surface area measurements⁶.

The present investigations relate to measurements of powder electrode potentials using different varieties of manganese dioxide and their change with alteration in the chemical nature of the powder. These have been supplemented by parallel studies on kinetics of decomposition of H_2O_2 catalysed by these powders and B.E.T. surface area measurements for comparing the conclusions reached from different experimental procedures.

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

Manganese dioxide was prepared by adopting different methods or slightly differing techniques and these were labelled VrA, VrB and VrC.

The variety A was prepared⁷ by dissolving 125 gms A.R. potassium permanganate in 1600 ml of distilled water and 450 ml of concentrated nitric acid were gradually added to

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the solution with stirring. The solution was then heated to boiling until MnO_2 precipitated out. The precipitate was digested for half an hour, filtered and washed free from electrolytes. It was then dried in an air oven at $110^\circ\text{-}115^\circ$ for $4\frac{1}{2}$ hrs. The dried mass was then finely powdered in a mortar.

The variety B (VrB) was obtained⁷ by oxidation of manganous sulphate with potassium permanganate and conc. nitric acid, 60 gms of $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R.) in 400 ml distilled water and 40 gm of K MnO_4 (A.R.) in 600 ml distilled water were mixed and 100 ml of conc. HNO_3 (A.R.) were added to the mixture. The latter was boiled till precipitation of manganese dioxide was complete. It was digested for half an hour, filtered, washed free from contaminating electrolytes. The mass was then dried at $110^\circ\text{-}115^\circ$ and powdered.

The preparation of VrC manganese dioxide was similar to that of VrA excepting that the volume of KMnO_4 was 1500 ml and that of conc. HNO_3 500 ml. The drying time was extended to 6 hrs. Besides these three varieties, VrD manganese dioxide represents mineral pyrolusite of E. Merck quality. VrE and VrF stand for further two preparations obtained from VrD sample by heating the latter to some predetermined temperatures viz. 300° and 700° respectively. The selection of these two temperatures was made on an examination of the thermogravimetric analytic curves of VrD to be described shortly.

The characterisation of the different samples of manganese dioxide (VrA to VrD) was made through thermal analyses, chemical analysis and by surface area measurements. The chemical analyses of the different samples of manganese dioxide (VrA to VrD) were carried out by estimating total manganese, available oxygen, loss in weight upto 150° and silica and mixed oxide (Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3) if any. On the basis of analytical data, the approximate formula of the compound appears in table I. Vr D contains besides MnO_2 , some Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 .

TABLE I

Varieties of MnO_2	Percentage loss on heating upto 150°	Percentage of Mn	Ratio of Mn available O_2	Approximate formula	Silica	Mixed oxides
Vr A	24.2	47.36	1 : 0.9	$\text{MnO}_{1.90}, 1.7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	nil	nil
Vr B	1.0	63.56	1 : 0.87	$\text{MnO}_{1.87}, 0.1\text{H}_2\text{O}$	nil	nil
Vr C	1.97	62.63	1 : 0.994	$\text{MnO}_{1.99}, 0.1\text{H}_2\text{O}$	nil	nil
Vr D	nil	56.6	1 : 1	MnO_2	2.44	7.96

No separate analysis was done for VrE as this was prepared from VrD on heating and VrF represented a new chemical species, chiefly a lower oxide of manganese as is evident from the thermogravimetric break of VrD sample (fig. 1). It is also evident from the detailed compositions of VrA, VrB and VrC that these must contain small proportions of lower oxides of manganese.

The thermogravimetric analyses of the samples (VrA to VrD) were done with the help of a derivatograph covering a temperature range $20^\circ\text{-}1000^\circ$. The T.G. curves are given

in fig. 1. Referring to VrD curve, the first break appearing at 530°-535° represents transformation⁸ of MnO₃ to Mn₂O₃. The next break just around 700° denotes a further change. Consequently VrE represents essentially MnO₂ and VrF, a lower oxide of manganese.

An idea as to the extent of available surface of these samples was obtained by determining the specific surface area on the basis of usual assumptions of multilayer adsorption, constancy of heat of adsorption from the second adsorbed layer onwards etc which generally go with the formulation of Brunauer Emmett and Teller adsorption isotherm. The surface area measured by B.E.T. method, are presented in Table IIA.

Powder electrode half cells were constructed with all the powders Vr A to Vr F using a common reference electrolyte KCl of different concentrations. These were coupled separately with a saturated calomel half cell and the powder electrode potentials were measured (Table IIA), in each case using Tomassi's device⁹ as has been reported in our previous work

TABLE IIA .

Calomel Electrode (saturated) = Anode ; Equilibration period = 16 to 20 hrs. Temp. = 30°

KCl as reference electrolyte in powder electrode chamber.

Powder sample	Surface area m ² /gm	Cell e.m.f. (volts)			
		1.0 N KCl	0.1 N KCl	0.01 N KCl	0.001 N KCl
Vr A	105.1	1.010	0.786	0.765	0.720
Vr B	100.4	0.960	0.909	0.863	0.833
Vr C	91.3	0.940	0.790	0.730	0.710
Vr D	4.28	0.355	0.356	0.365	0.370
Vr E	4.5	0.280	—	—	—
Vr F	4.49	0.070	—	—	—

TABLE IIB

Calomel Electrode = Anode ; Equilibration period = 16 to 20 hours.

Reference Electrolyte 0.1 N KCl ; Temp. = 30°

Powder sample	Cell e.m.f. in volts								
	Pt contact electrode fully inside powder phase			Pt- contact partially inside the powder		Pt- contact fully dragged out of the powder		Cell voltage with a separate Pt electrode dipped in the same reference electrolyte	
	12 noon	1 P.M.	2 P.M.	3 P.M.	4 P.M.	5 P.M.	6 P.M.	12 P.M.	6 P.M.
Vr A	0.786	0.786	0.783	0.780	0.777	0.738	0.732	0.100	0.073
Vr B	0.909	0.904	0.906	0.910	0.909	0.840	0.840	0.114	0.120
Vr C	0.790	0.790	0.791	0.778	0.778	0.736	0.730	0.094	0.095
Vr D	0.352	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.353	0.318	0.307	0.127	0.041

8. C. Duval, "Inorganic Thermogravimetric Analysis", Elsevier Publishing Co., 1963, 313.

9. W. Tomassi, H. Jankowska and M. Prokopowicz, *Bull. Classe. Des. Sciences. Acad. Roy. de Belg.*, 1957, 3, 195.

FIG 1

Weight of the sample taken

Vr. A 0.500 gm.

Vr. B 0.790 gm

Vr. C 0.440 gm.

Vr. D 1.860 gm.

on barium sulphate. The amount of powder used in each powder half-cell was 0.5 gm for Vr A, B and C and 1.0 gm for Vr D, E and F. The volume of reference electrolyte put in contact with the powder for 16 to 20 hrs for attainment of equilibrium was 50 ml in each case. The potentials of bare platinum wire in contact with the reference electrolyte, but out of contact with the powder, are recorded in Table IIB. The potential values of half immersed Pt wire (partially inside the powder material and partially exposed to reference electrolyte) also appear in the same table.

Two other obvious phenomena in which the surface plays a prominent role are adsorption from solution by powders and catalytic activity in heterogeneous kinetics. Adsorption experiments with each variety of the powders Vr A to Vr F were performed by keeping these powders separately in contact with the 1.0M KCL (which served as reference electrolyte in the powder half cell in potential measurements). The analysis of the equilibrium solution for chloride ion content showed almost negligible adsorption by all the powders.

The well known catalytic power of the oxides of manganese in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solution was next studied with each powder Vr A to Vr F. The reaction solution was a mixture 90 ml of H_2O_2 (2.643 gms H_2O_2 /lit), 10 ml distilled water, and 0.01 gm

of catalytic powder. Both titrimetric and gas evolution methods were investigated, but of the two the titrimetric procedure yielded more reproducible results. The temperature ranged from 20° to 40°. The complete table containing the kinetic data including the heat of activation, entropy of activation and the frequency factor are embodied in Table III.

DISCUSSION

In the first place we note from one set of sample data (Table IIB) out of many such collected, that the potential of the Pt- electrode in the reference electrolyte is rather unsteady and quite different from the value observed when the electrode is fully immersed inside the powder. This is similar to the situation observed in the case of BaSO₄ powder electrode¹ We can, therefore, expect these powder potential values (Vr A to Vr F) to be an index of the surface nature of the powder concerned. It may be noticed from Table IIA that the specific surface areas of the powders decrease from rather high values to rather low ones in the series Vr A to Vr D. The values of surface areas viz. 4.28, 4.5 and 4.49 m²/gm for Vr D, Vr E and Vr F respectively do not really reflect any difference since the errors involved in the B.E.T. method for small surface areas may be quite considerable and overshadow the real differences or the order of decrease in the series D, E and F.

TABLE III

Varieties of Manganese Dioxide	20°	Rate constant $k \times 10^3$ min.			40°	Heat of activation K.Cal/mole	Entropy of Activation c.u.	Frequency Factor
		25°	30°	35°				
Vr A	11.5	13.8	18.2	29.9	33.8	11.3	-37.8	10 ^{6.4}
Vr B	10.9	14.2	15.7	16.9	21.6	6.4	-54.3	10 ^{2.6}
Vr C	13.3	16.1	21.6	24.2	28.3	6.9	-52.2	10 ^{3.3}
Vr D	—	1.60	1.80	2.60	3.90	14.4	-32.3	10 ^{7.6}
Vr E	—	2.90	4.20	5.60	—	11.5	-40.2	10 ^{5.6}
Vr F	—	1.20	—	2.70	4.30	14.8	-30.8	10 ^{7.9}

The parallelism demonstrated by the powder potential values (in terms of the e.m.f. of the cells, Tables IIA) with the surface area in the series Vr A to Vr D is quite interesting. The decrease in surface area value is accompanied by diminution in the e.m.f. values. When the reference electrolyte is normal KCl, but the parallelism vanishes when values for low concentrations of the reference electrolyte are examined. A sharply low potential value for Vr D is characterised by a correspondingly low surface area value. The potential data for Vr D and Vr E, however, indicate a small drop although the surface area values, according to the foregoing discussion, may be taken to be approximately the same. The potential and the surface area values of VrF cannot, however, be compared with any of the series Vr A to Vr E, since the latter are primarily manganese dioxide and chemically Vr F, obtained by heating Vr D to 700°, is a lower oxide of manganese (mainly Mn₂O₃).

A moot point arises here as to why the comparison between the specific surface areas and powder potential values of Vr A to Vr E should hold for rather high conc. of potassium chloride (1 N), while the order of decrease in potential values does not run parallel to that

of surface area for low concentrations of KCl (vide Table IIA). Possibly the indirect idea obtainable about surface area through powder potential measurement is likely to be best represented under such conditions of electrolyte concentration as will help towards greater adsorption by the powder.

On the other hand, if one turns to the kinetics of decomposition of H_2O_2 catalysed by manganese oxide powder, the kinetic properties will be dependent on the surface nature and the composition of the powders. The way powder potentials can be indicative of the kinetic properties should comprise those values which are measured under zero or negligible conc. of potassium chloride serving as reference electrolyte in the powder electrode chamber. This expectation is borne out by examining the curves (Fig. 2) depicting the variation of powder potential values (in terms of the e.m.f. of cells) with logarithm of concentrations of reference electrolyte KCl for the samples Vr A, Vr B, Vr C, Vr D. The extrapolations of the curves to region $\log C = -5$ or -6 , if permissible, show that the powder potentials decrease in the series Vr B, Vr C, Vr A, Vr D. The kinetic data indicate (Table III) that the energies of activation increase in the order $B \rightarrow C \rightarrow A \rightarrow D$, the values ranging from 6.4 K Cal to 14.4 K Cal. Qualitative correlations between powder potentials and energies

Fig 2

of activation have been indicated by Tomassi⁵ in the decomposition of formic acid in presence of copper powder as catalyst. Similar sequence is preserved for the entropies of activation which gradually tend towards less negative values in the series $B \rightarrow C \rightarrow A \rightarrow D$.

The choice of $\log C = -5$ or -6 for comparison of potential values as mentioned above is made on the supposition that at this concentration, which is sufficiently low, the powder potential values for different samples would show little difference from the values at zero concentration of the reference electrolyte.

Davidovich¹⁰ sought to explain the behaviour of powder electrodes by attributing to the Pt- electrode the function of an indicator electrode for the hydronium ions. In support of his contention, he cites identical potential values recorded by the Pt-wire both when in contact with the powder (*e.g.* ZnO, Al₂O₃ etc.) and also when in contact with the filtered reference electrolyte alone. Careful experiments with the present series of manganese oxide yield data which do not confirm Davidovich's view. Powder potential values (Table IIB) are sharply different from potential values of the Pt-wire in contact with the reference electrolyte, the values being recorded over a period of about 4 to 6 hrs. subsequent to the lapse of the equilibration period for 20 hrs. However, if the Pt-wire, used to record the powder potential, be drawn out of the powder phase and allowed to be completely surrounded by the reference electrolyte, then an immediate measurement of potential shows value very near the powder potential value, but the former goes on changing sharply with time. Even the powder potential values recorded by the Pt-wire which is half drawn out of the powder phase after equilibration tends to depart from the equilibrium value with time. These data, therefore, do not corroborate Davidovich's views on powder potentials at least in relation to manganese dioxide.

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